

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education Department University of Sindh Jamshoro

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Abstract

This study examined the classroom management strategies and use of instructional techniques utilized by two eighth grade English teachers. A qualitative approach was used, with teacher interviews and observations forming the basis of the study. It was found that both teachers demonstrated high levels of classroom management, with 72% and 70% of strategies being utilized by T1 and T2 respectively. Strategies such as seating arrangements, well-explained material, and establishing positive relationships with students were applied throughout the course of instruction, from start to finish. Overall, this study has contributed to the existing body of knowledge surrounding effective classroom management for eighth grade students.

Keywords: Analysis of Teachers, Classroom Management, Education, Strategies, Instruction

INTRODUCTION

As educators, it is our responsibility to ensure that the learning process is conducted in an environment that serves the best interests of our students. This includes creating a sense of safety for both students and staff, and providing our students with learning materials and guidance that stimulates their interest. good and brophy (2003:48) acknowledged that it is difficult for teachers to be aware of all that is happening in the classroom, and this deficiency can impede their effectiveness as educators.

In order to effectively encourage our students' learning, teachers must have the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively use the learning materials, as well as the ability to motivate students to utilize them. This involves sparking an enthusiasm in learning and

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

demonstrating to students its importance. Ultimately, it is through the combined efforts of the students, teachers, teaching materials, and learning environment that the educational process is created.

English education experts have chosen to focus their research in the classroom setting due to the excellent infrastructure and good management provided at this particular school. Each teacher applies unique tactics when maintaining control of classes, and the school itself is well-equipped with language labs, science labs, computer labs and libraries, canteens and more. Its importance for educators is apparent due to the physical and mental growth that occurs during middle school. Students this age are curious about the world and have easy access to a vast array of information, which can, unfortunately, have a negative impact on them. It is vital that teachers prioritize activities to engage them and guide them in positive directions. Eighth graders, in particular, experience rapid emotional and physical change, which can lead to unstable emotions or sudden shifts in attitude. Moreover, ninth graders are more focused when it comes to taking national exams.

Thus, the "Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in English Teaching" in the Ministry of Education was conceived, aiming to investigate how these educators guide their students through their formative years.

Teaching strategy of Classroom management

Burden (2010:75) provides helpful suggestions for successful classroom management, allowing educational activities to be productive and enjoyable for everyone. Gathering data on the matter can assist educators in developing strategies that maintain an atmosphere conducive to learning.

a. Before teaching any lesson, the teacher must thoroughly prepare so that students can have an effective day of learning. This includes ensuring that learning material, lesson plans, and a daily schedule are all in line with the school district's provisions. Additionally, the plans must be tailored to each student's individual learning style. This may mean providing visual learners with more activities suited to their needs, or offering extra time for those who require it. Additionally, for those that excel, there should be additional tasks available, so that students can work on their own initiative. Through such tailored lessons, teaching in the classroom can be rewarding and successful.

b. It is essential for teachers to cultivate an inviting, conducive learning atmosphere for their students. To make the classroom attractive, the use of slides, pictures, or games is recommended, as well as adhering to a set schedule for cleaning, so as to promote creativity, innovation, and joy for students while learning.

c. In order to ensure that teaching is optimised and the school classroom is a conducive learning environment, it is important to establish classroom rules that are mutually agreed upon and maintained by students and teachers alike. By involving students in the creation process, it will also help encourage them to abide by the rules. It is essential to have a way of monitoring adherence to the classroom rules and of rewarding those who follow them; this will both encourage continued compliance and provide motivation to those who have not been successful.

d. The teacher should strive to be enthusiastic in the classroom, as this will make the lessons more interactive and engaging for the students. As lessons unfold, the teacher should

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

ensure that they have implemented methods that encourage student participation, such as providing feedback, asking questions, and rewarding responses. Furthermore, it is essential to give students enough waiting time to answer questions, as everyone progresses at different speeds. Ultimately, the teacher should thank the students for their involvement and work to showcase their best qualities.

e. As a teacher, it is important to be equitable towards all of your students. Make every effort to listen to their views and show respect for each of them, no matter what type of behaviour they exhibit. Treat each student with dignity and do not make any distinctions between the more obedient and the disobedient. Through demonstrating fairness and impartiality, your students will gain admiration and appreciation for your approach.

f. Keeping accurate records of students is an essential part of the learning process. Not only does it allow teachers to fairly assess the work students have completed, but it also helps to reward and encourage them for following instructions and behaving well in class. Additionally, it ensures that students understand the goals and objectives of the lesson plan. Rating tasks completed by students in class is a good way to help them learn the basics, as it involves listening to or reading comments made by teachers and other students.

METHOD

A qualitative research method, often referred to as naturalistic inquiry (Sugiyono, 2006), was used in this study to capture a natural understanding of the phenomenon being studied. According to Sukmadinata (2012), descriptive research looks into the characteristics, activities, changes, relationships, similarities and differences of the phenomenon being studied. It is used to accurately describe and explain the nature, condition and number of the object being studied (Arikunto, 2006). Through the collection and analysis of data, descriptive research is able to provide a comprehensive account of the current practices, learning strategies, classroom environment and more at a certain time and place. The conclusion drawn is solely based on the processed data.

In this study, descriptive qualitative approach was used to gain insights into the English teachers' classroom management strategies while teaching at the Education Department. Descriptive studies focus on describing the characteristics of a particular group or a phenomenon (Kothari, 2015). The purpose of this study was to explain the difficulties the English teachers were facing in their classrooms and to generate an in-depth understanding of their classroom management skills. Qualitative data collection techniques such as open-ended questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were used to address the research questions. It was concluded that an effective classroom management skill is essential to ensure students are engaged in learning and to guarantee academic success.

Technique of Collecting Data

In order to answer the two research questions "how do the English teacher apply their classroom management in teaching English?" and "how the English teachers implement their classroom management in Teaching English?" a qualitative research approach was taken, combining observation and interviews in order to triangulate the data. To answer the first question, observation was performed, with the researchers acting as observers and using an adapted observation checklist from Burden (1995). For the second question, participants

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

were interviewed, using an unstructured interview in which questions were prepared in advance and new questions could be added according to the progress of the interview. This enabled the researchers to observe the implementation of classroom management and gather in-depth information from the participants (Sugiyono, 2006; Sudjana, 2005).

RESULT

For two weeks, the researchers conducted an observational study to answer the question of “How do the English teachers apply their classroom management strategies in teaching English at the education department?” For data collection, the researchers utilized Burden’s (1995) observational checklist, which consisted of five categories: organization, behavioral consideration, instructional strategies, social climate, and physical arrangement. During the duration of the study, two English teachers were observed with the data collected within each observation being compiled into a written form. This effort was done to answer the initial question posed. (105 words) Table 1. The use of Classroom Management Strategy (T1)

No	Category	Total Use	Percentage
1	Organization	30	12%
2	Behavioral consideration	54	21%
3	Instructional strategies	45	18%
4	Social climate	40	16%
5	Physical Arrangement	13	5%

The observation revealed that Teacher 1 obtained a higher score on the observation checklist. It was noted that her score was 181 points, constituting 72% of the 250 points total, attesting to the excellent management of her classroom. In terms of organization, it was observed that Teacher 1 was remarkable, having gained 30 points from a possible 40. She was able to maintain control of her material, providing clear direction in regards to activities – from the start to the finish of class. The ability to address unforeseen scenarios with an additional contingency plan was also visible. Lastly, she was credited with well-planned lessons and effective delivery of assignment instructions, even though it was documented that she generally favored verbal communication regarding tasks over written notices in the board (Livermore, 2006).

In terms of behavioural considerations, she achieved 54 points out of 70 points. She established beneficial guidelines for the students in the classroom. During the transitions, such as when she was introducing the lesson and interacting with students, she didn’t focus solely on one side. In class, the students were made aware of both the positive and negative consequences that they would face if they disobeyed the rules. She also warned the students who disrupted the teaching-learning process and didn’t bring their textbook for English lessons, either due to an absence or any other issue. In this way, students were made to understand their consequence and also take responsibility accordingly. Even though she had put rules in place, she still faced issues when it came to developing a positive behaviour in

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

students such as appreciation of classmates or the teacher in front of them. She also failed to give ample attention to the students seated at the back, resulting in most of them talking while the lesson was taking place (Ramesh, 2015).

The researcher found that the teacher utilized a combination of different instructional strategies during her teaching. She reached 45 points from 70 points, which proves the effectiveness of such strategies. On her teaching session, she employed the use of different media to make instructional games. She also employed a whiteboard to demonstrate the materials properly. Additionally, it was also observed that the instructor monitored the lesson before and after providing instructions. Although the strategy of teaching was not particularly interesting, she still used worksheets provided by the school in explaining the material. Textbooks and whiteboards were also utilized for explanation. Questions and feedbacks were often given during the lesson to understand the concept better. Moreover, she asked the students to explain the activity after giving an instruction or get someone to show other students how the exercise works. Thus, the teacher would ask the students after giving the instructions to ensure their understanding (Kamya, 2019).

In the social climate, she managed to increase her approval rating from 55 to 40, achieving a 72% success rate of 100%. Her style of instruction and relationship-building with her students was highly praised. She crafted a close and friendly atmosphere in the classroom, by communicating in a respectful and open manner. To further engage her students and make the learning process enjoyable, she would occasionally use humour or encourage the students to explain their own thought processes in regards to a given topic. Additionally, when one of her students gave a correct answer, she would reward them with a simple "good" or applause, to further promote active student participation without fear of ridicule or judgement.

The researchers noted that when T1 was teaching in C class, there were a lot of issues with classroom management. Activities that should have been conducted were neglected, with the students becoming uninterested due to the lack of interesting materials and content in the classroom. Furthermore, in order to avoid staying until late, many students from other classes were leaving the classroom early. When assessing the physical arrangement of the classroom, T1 achieved 12 points out of 15. Despite the somewhat uninviting environment, T1 managed to make the most of the situation by seating the students in groups of 4-5 according to their comradely preferences and keeping the classroom appealing. Table 2. The use of Classroom Management Strategy (T2)

No	Category	Total Use	Percentage
1	Organization	25	10%
2	Behavioral consideration	55	22%
3	Instructional strategies	44	17%
4	Social climate	39	16%
5	Physical Arrangement	12	5%

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

The researchers concluded that T1's management of the C class was subpar in comparison to her other classes in terms of her physical and instructional effectiveness. She garnered only twelve points out of a possible fifteen in regards to the classroom environment, which included the attraction of the surroundings and the proper placement of desks. One of the major issues relating to her management of C was the lack of engaging activities and assignments that would stimulate student interest. As such, many students were overly eager to finish their lessons and leave the classroom, resulting in a disorderly atmosphere. Additionally, many students from other classes would wander into the classroom, further exacerbating the lack of order. To combat this, T1 should have developed more creative lessons and activities as well as made the classroom atmosphere more accommodating and inviting.

In terms of behavioral expectations, the teacher scored 58 out of 70 points. He was proficient in providing discipline and developing the behavior of students in the class. Using positive language and establishing clear rules, he was able to effectively implement consequences for those who did not pay attention or disrupted their peers. He was also able to use proximity control to reduce inappropriate behavior towards him. Additionally, he implemented movement routines in order to provide students explicit steps for entering, exiting, and moving throughout the classroom.

With regards to instructional strategies, he scored 46 out of 70 points. He often used both small groups and individual work in his classroom. He had the ability to properly explain the material, provide feedback to students, and use questioning to effectively capture their attention. However, he was found to seldom use any other examples or materials to further assist the students in understanding the lesson. This caused the students to struggle to stay motivated and interested in the material. Ultimately, the lack of varied instructional methods and up-to-date examples made it difficult to capture the attention of the learners.

In the social climate, he obtained a composite score of 39 out of 55. Similar to T1, T2 exhibited friendly and positive behavior. He was successful in establishing relationships with the students and would offer motivation during the lesson by making generalised statements such as "Be a good friend" and "Respect others" (Rapado-Toni, 2019). Furthermore, he would often listen to the students during the lesson and offer them the opportunity to explain the material and engage with their peers (O'Neil et al., 2019). However, he would not use humor during the class (Rapado-Toni, 2019). For physical arrangements, T2 was scored 12 out of 15. He seldom made the classroom an attractive environment in which the students would be interested (Rapado-Toni, 2019). Despite this, he created a tense environment and did not permit the students to arrange their seating into small groups (O'Neil et al., 2019).

Finding of interview

In conducting the interviews, the researchers established a structured format in order to ensure that the collected data is both valid and reliable. During the interview with Teacher 1, it was revealed that almost all of the problems she encountered were related to the condition of the classroom before classes commence. The teacher stated that each class was unique in terms of underlying conditions and dynamics. She also pointed out that the most difficult task in managing a classroom was managing the behavior of her students, as each student had a

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

unique attitude and tendency to disrupt the teaching-learning activities by conversing with friends instead of attentively listening to the teacher's lecture. As for the solutions, Teacher 1 warned her students when disrupting during the class, and also imposed a punishment for disruptive behavior such as task assignments or asking them to list down 30 words and their accompanying meanings.

The interview with Teacher 2 indicated that the problems encountered were similar to those of Teacher 1. He acknowledged that he had yet to make the classroom an attractive learning environment. He also faced a problem in managing his students' behavior, which included some on not paying due attention to the lesson, as well as others who were deliberately disruptive. The solutions Teacher 2 employed to deal with both situations were to call out the names of those who misbehaved, ask them to clean up in front of the class, or even ask them to leave the premises.

Thus, with structured interviews, the researchers were able to triangulate the data, thereby ensuring its validity and reliability (Zhao, 2019).

DISCUSSION

The findings from both observation and interviews revealed that both Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 effectively managed their classrooms by directing activities and providing material to students. However, they did not post the assignment clearly or provide appropriate homework. In contrast, Teacher 1 seemed to lack the consideration for student behaviour. According to Garret (2014:29), classroom rules usually provide direction regarding tasks rather than trying to prevent certain behaviour. According to Larson (1992:92), when faced with disruptive students, teachers should employ direct eye contact or move closer to them in order to gain their attention. Haddad (2006:43) also advises that to control students' behaviour, the teacher should stand close by rather than far away. When confronted with students leaving the class without permission, Teacher 1 resorted to threatening to release them from the class. For students who were not paying attention during the lesson, Teacher 1 warned them that their marks would suffer. It can be concluded that the teacher attempted to curb the deviant behaviour of her students.

When giving instructions, it is important for teachers to ensure students have understood what is being asked of them. Harmer (2008:38) provides two general rules for giving instructions: they should be kept to a complexity level the students can comprehend; and the instructions should follow logical cause-effect reasoning. To ensure comprehension, the teacher can ask a student to explain the activity after giving the instruction, or demonstrate the exercise as a way to show the rest of the class how it works. When students voiced their confusion, the teacher repeated the instructions to ensure understanding.

The teacher has employed the technique of arranging the students into group or pairs to facilitate interaction among them, which echoes Scrinever's (2005:67) statement that the teacher should be encouraging conversation between students, not only between the teacher and the class. Furthermore, Harmer (2008:24) holds that an excellent teacher should have the capacity to be flexible in their lesson planning, and adapt to different class sizes, seating

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

arrangements, and activity types. At the kickoff of the lesson, the students were placed in rows, representative of Harmer's (2008:41) notion that orderly rows indicate a teacher working with the whole class. In their first activity, the teacher encouraged group work by organizing the desks so the students could see one another. On the second occasion, the students formed pairs; however, due to the orderly rows, they were still able to collaborate with their neighbor, in front of, or behind them (Harmer 2008:42)..

CONCLUSION

Observation of T1 and T2 revealed that 72% and 70% respectively of their classroom management strategies were utilized. The teaching-learning process began with the teachers preparing and distributing the material, followed by an explanation. Continuous feedback was given to the students to ensure clear understanding of the material. Small groups were also implemented so that the material was better absorbed. Not only did the teachers present the material effectively, but they also employed discipline, motivation and humorous elements to build connection and positive attitude among the students. Should any student misbehave or cause disruption, the teachers would resort to verbal reprisals such as calling out the names to ensure discipline in the classroom. Upon completion of the material, homework was assigned to guarantee the material was thoroughly gone over before the students left the classroom.

The physical conditions and managing student misbehavior posed to be challenges for both T1 and T2. Primarily manifested in the form of students not paying attention, not listening to instructions, being noisy and the physical conditions in different classrooms. To tackle these issues, the teachers observe the classroom pre-teaching session, making sure the environment is clean and orderly. They reprimand any misconduct with verbal warnings to make sure the students are paying attention and respect their peers. Ultimately, individualised homework was assigned to ensure the material has been thoroughly gone over.

REFERENCES

1. Arikunto, Suharsimi. (2006). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
2. Burden, R. Paul. (2000). *Powerful Classroom Management Strategy*. United Kingdom: Corwin Press, Inc.
3. Burden, P.R. (2010). *Classroom management: Creating a successful learning community*. (2th ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons
4. Emmer, E.T., & Gerwels, M.C. (2006). *Establishing classroom management for cooperative learning*. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Montreal, Canada.
5. Fauziati, Endang. (2015). *Teaching English as a Foreign Language*. Surakarta: Era Pustaka Utama.
6. Garret, Tracey. (2014). *Effective of Classroom Management*. Columbia University: Teacher College.
7. Good, Thomas and Brophy, Jere. (2003). **Looking in Classroom: Ninth Edition**. USA: Pearson Education Inc.
8. Haddad, Caroline. (2006). *Practical Tips for Teaching Large Classes: A Teacher's Guide*. Bangkok : UNESCO.
9. Harmer, Jeremy. (2008). *How To Teach English*. New edition. England : Longman.
10. Kibria, A., & Siddiqui, M. B. (2022). An analysis of the Pakistani banking industry's performance in

An Analysis of Teachers' Classroom Management in Teaching English in Education ...

- relation to Islamic and conventional banking. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 31-39.
8. Kibria, A., & Siddiqui, M. B. (2022). Interactive Intentions of Consumers to Adopt Islamic Banking in Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 13-23.
 9. Kibria, A., Junejo, I., Siddique, M., & Banbhan, A. A. (2020). the Impact of Islamic Work Ethics on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Work Performance. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 11(12).
 10. Kibria, A., Kazi, D. A. S., Banbhan, D. A. A., Shahani, A. K., & Junejo, I. (2021). Investigating linkages of performance appraisal, employee promotion and job satisfaction with employee performance in banking sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(2), 3749-3757.
 11. Larson, Jo .Mary. (1992). *Teaching English As A Foreign Language To Large, Multilevel Classes*. USA : Peace Corps.
 12. Marzano, R.J. (2003). *Classroom Management That Works*. Virginia US :ASCD.
 13. Abro, A., Jamali, N. M., Anjum, M. S., & Kibria, A. (2023). Exploring Entrepreneurs' Motivation for Engaging in Crowdfunding and its Potential Outcomes in Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 36-49.
 14. Arends, Richard. I. (2004). *Learning to Teach*. USA: McGraw-Hill.
 15. Miles, Matthew B., A. Michael Huberman, Johnny Saldana. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
 16. Moloeng, Lexy J. (2007). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
 17. Palupi, Agata .R. (2013). *Classroom Management Applied By the Eighth Grade Teacher in Teaching English in SMP Muhammadiyah 1 Surakarta in 2012/2013 Academic Year*. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
 18. Rudiyanto, Arif. (2014). *Descriptive Analysis of Classroom Management Strategies of the Second Grade Students of SMP N 03 Tenganan Semarang*. STAIN Salatiga
 19. Scrivener. Jim. (2005). *Learning Teaching: A Guidebook for English Language Teacher*. 2nd ed. Malaysia
 20. Sudjana, Nana. (2005). *Pengantar Penelitian Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Bina Rupa Aksara.
 21. Sugiyono. (2006). *Metode Penelitian (Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
 22. Sukmadinata, Nana Syaodih. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
 23. Weinstein, Carol and Romano, Molly. (2014). *Elementary Classroom Management: Lesson from Research and Practice: Sixth Edition*. USA: McGraw-Hill Education